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Supplementary Information for

Origin of late Cenozoic basaltic magmatism in Inner Mongolia, NE China: Constraints from Sr–Nd–Hf–Pb–Mo–He isotopes

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Research interest: igneous petrology and geochemistry

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Introduction:

The supporting information provides photomicrograph (b) of the Chifeng basalts ([Supplementary Fig. 1](#)); diagrams of (a) $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ versus MgO (wt.%), (b) ϵNd versus MgO (wt.%), (c) ϵHf versus MgO (wt.%) and (d) Nb/La versus MgO (wt.%) for the Chifeng basalts and the previously published Chifeng basalts in NE China ([Supplementary Fig. 2](#)), diagrams of (a) Ni (ppm) versus MgO (wt.%), (b) $\text{CaO}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ versus MgO (wt.%) and (c) Al_2O_3 (wt.%) versus MgO (wt.%) for the Chifeng basalts and the previously published Chifeng basalts in NE China ([Supplementary Fig. 3](#)), diagrams of (a) Mo/Ce ratios versus Loss on ignition (LOI) values, (b) $\delta^{98/95}\text{Mo}$ values versus LOI values, (c) Mo/Ce ratios versus chemical index of alteration (CIA) and (d) $\delta^{98/95}\text{Mo}$ values versus CIA for the Chifeng basalts ([Supplementary Fig. 4](#)); detailed locations and age of the Chifeng basalts ([Supplementary Table 1](#)); whole rock trace element data of standard rocks ([Supplementary Table 2](#)); whole rock Sr-Nd-Hf-Pb data of standard rocks ([Supplementary Table 3](#)); whole rock Mo isotopes data of seawater and standard rocks ([Supplementary Table 4](#)); He isotope data of olivines of Chifeng basalts ([Supplementary Table 5](#)); and whole-rock major-trace elements and Sr-Nd-Pb-Hf-Mo isotope data of the Chifeng basalts ([Supplementary Table 6](#)).

Supplementary Figure 1: photomicrographs of the Chifeng basalts (a-b).

Note: Ol, olivine; Cpx, clinopyroxene.

Supplementary Figure 2: diagrams of (a) $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ versus MgO (wt.%), (b) ϵNd versus MgO (wt.%), (c) ϵHf versus MgO (wt.%) and (d) Nb/La versus MgO (wt.%) for the Chifeng basalts and the previously published Chifeng basalts in NE China. Previously published data of Chifeng basalts are from Wang et al. (2015), Guo et al. (2016, 2020), and Pang et al. (2019).

Supplementary Figure 3: diagrams of (a) Ni (ppm) versus MgO (wt.%), (b) CaO/Al₂O₃ versus MgO (wt.%) and (c) Al₂O₃ (wt.%) versus MgO (wt.%) for the Chifeng basalts and the previously published Chifeng basalts in NE China. Data sources are the same as in supplementary

Figure 2.

Supplementary Figure 4: diagrams of (a) Mo/Ce ratios versus Loss on ignition (LOI) values, (b) $\delta^{98/95}\text{Mo}$ values versus LOI values, (c) Mo/Ce ratios versus chemical index of alteration (CIA) and (d) $\delta^{98/95}\text{Mo}$ values versus CIA for the Chifeng basalts.

Supplementary Table 1: The detailed locations and age of the Chifeng basalts.

Sample	Location (N, E)		Age
2001	43°02'13.80"	118°12'26.40"	2.8-9.7Ma (Wang et al., 2015)
2004	42°51'59.40"	118°06'49.80"	2.8-9.7Ma (Wang et al., 2015)
2006	42°59'54.00"	118°00'56.40"	2.8-9.7Ma (Wang et al., 2015)
2012	42°49'33.60"	117°37'56.40"	2.8-9.7Ma (Wang et al., 2015)
2013	42°48'54.00"	117°39'32.40"	2.8-9.7Ma (Wang et al., 2015)
2015	42°49'7.80"	117°43'38.40"	2.8-9.7Ma (Wang et al., 2015)
2016	42°49'3.00"	117°48'0.600"	2.8-9.7Ma (Wang et al., 2015)
2017	42°46'39.00"	117°46'56.40"	2.8-9.7Ma (Wang et al., 2015)
2018	42°46'45.60"	117°47'2.40"	2.8-9.7Ma (Wang et al., 2015)
2019	42°44'45.60"	117°45'48.00"	2.8-9.7Ma (Wang et al., 2015)
2020	42°51'1.800"	118°41'52.88"	2.8-9.7Ma (Wang et al., 2015)
2024	42°40'2.400"	118°32'16.20"	2.8-9.7Ma (Wang et al., 2015)
2025	42°38'17.40"	118°25'33.00"	2.8-9.7Ma (Wang et al., 2015)
2026	42°37'51.60"	118°22'46.80"	2.8-9.7Ma (Wang et al., 2015)
2027	42°37'46.80"	118°22'26.40"	2.8-9.7Ma (Wang et al., 2015)
2028	42°34'13.80"	118°30'51.60"	2.8-9.7Ma (Wang et al., 2015)
2031	42°39'41.40"	117°59'55.80"	2.8-9.7Ma (Wang et al., 2015)
2033	42°42'8.40"	118°01'26.40"	2.8-9.7Ma (Wang et al., 2015)
2042	42°08'36.60"	117°02'7.80"	2.8-9.7Ma (Wang et al., 2015)
2043A	42°08'0.06"	117°05'43.20"	2.8-9.7Ma (Wang et al., 2015)
2043B	42°07'1.2"	117°06'43.80"	2.8-9.7Ma (Wang et al., 2015)

Supplementary Table 2: whole-rock major-trace elements of standard rocks.

	This study	Ref.	This study	Ref.
	BCR-2	BCR-2	BHVO-2	BHVO-2
Sc	33.4	33	32	32
V	423	416	319	317
Cr	16.5	16.5	296	280
Co	37.7	37	45	45
Ni	12	13	122	119
Cu	16.5	18.4	126	127
Zn	133	133	98.9	103
Ga	22	23	21.5	21.7
Rb	48.1	46.9	9.49	9.11
Sr	340	340	397	396
Y	36.3	37	26.5	26
Zr	186	184	171	172
Nb	12.6	12.6	18.7	18.1
Cs	1.19	1.1	0.0997	0.1
Ba	709	677	134	131
La	25.4	24.9	15.3	15.2
Ce	53.8	52.9	37.7	37.5
Pr	6.91	6.7	5.35	5.35
Nd	29	28.7	24.6	24.5
Sm	6.6	6.58	6.17	6.07

Eu	1.94	1.96	2.05	2.07
Gd	6.66	6.75	6.24	6.24
Tb	1.08	1.07	0.955	0.92
Dy	6.3	6.41	5.24	5.31
Ho	1.3	1.28	0.983	0.98
Er	3.61	3.66	2.47	2.54
Tm	0.541	0.54	0.34	0.33
Yb	3.35	3.38	1.97	2
Lu	0.505	0.5	0.278	0.27
Hf	4.76	4.9	4.29	4.36
Ta	0.768	0.78	1.14	1.14
Pb	9.99	11	1.49	1.6
Th	5.94	5.7	1.23	1.22
U	1.69	1.69	0.42	0.4

Note: values for the reference materials are from GeoREM (<http://georem.mpch-mainz.gwdg.de/>)

Supplementary Table 3: whole-rock Sr-Nd-Hf-Pb isotopes of standard rocks.

	This study	Ref.	This study	Ref.
Sample	BCR-2	BCR-2	BHVO-2	BHVO-2
$^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$	0.705016±8	0.705026 ± 20	0.703488±13	0.703480 ±8
$^{143}\text{Nd}/^{144}\text{Nd}$	0.512643± 4	0.512638 ± 15	0.512989±4	0.512982±8
$^{176}\text{Hf}/^{177}\text{Hf}$	0.282870±4	0.282869 ±9	0.283119±4	0.283105 ± 11
$^{208}\text{Pb}/^{204}\text{Pb}$	38.733±2	38.725 ±22	38.2067±1	38.236±18
$^{207}\text{Pb}/^{204}\text{Pb}$	15.621±1	15.621 ± 4	15.523±1	15.533±9
$^{206}\text{Pb}/^{204}\text{Pb}$	18.767±1	18.753 ±8	18.624±1	18.647±24

Note: values for the reference materials are from GeoREM (<http://georem.mpch-mainz.gwdg.de/>)

Supplementary Table 4: whole-rock Mo isotopes of seawater and geological reference materials.

	This study	Ref.	This study	Ref.
Samples	$\delta^{98/95}\text{Mo}$	$\delta^{98/95}\text{Mo}$	Mo (ppm)	Mo (ppm)
IAPSO Seawater	2.09±5	2.03+6	0.01	0.01
GSR-3	-0.46±4	-0.51±4	3.07	2.92
AGV-2	-0.15±4	-0.14±5	1.97	1.93

Note: values for the reference materials are from [Zhao et al. \(2016\)](#).

Supplementary Table 5: He isotope of olivines of Chifeng basalts.

	$^3\text{He}/^4\text{He}$ (Ra)	1s	^4He ccSTP/g
Olivine of cf2025	1.85	0.06	2.3E-09
Olivine of cf2117	3.73	0.08	2.1E-08
Olivine of cf2116	5.54	0.56	2.6E-08
Olivine of cf2120a	2.53	0.08	2.1E-09
Olivine of cf2136	2.45	0.08	2.5E-09
Olivine of cf2137	1.00	0.05	1.2E-09
Olivine of cf2018	0.76	0.03	1.4E-08

Supplementary Table 6: whole-rock major-trace elements, and Sr-Nd-Hf-Pb-Mo isotopes of the Chifeng basalts.

	2001	2004	2006	2012	2013	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
SiO ₂	49.98	48.16	47.05	46.29	50.01	50.31	47.45	46.85	50.97	45.07	50.46
TiO ₂	1.84	2.25	2.34	2.50	1.97	2.06	2.44	2.46	2.03	2.49	2.11
Al ₂ O ₃	13.96	13.36	13.94	13.26	13.70	14.11	12.73	12.81	14.19	12.66	14.48
Fe ₂ O ₃ T	11.90	12.10	12.73	12.70	12.14	12.16	13.07	12.61	11.78	13.08	11.25
MnO	0.15	0.14	0.16	0.16	0.13	0.15	0.16	0.15	0.15	0.16	0.13
MgO	8.68	8.95	9.25	9.34	7.41	7.61	9.47	9.66	7.49	9.92	7.00
CaO	8.28	8.12	8.60	8.55	7.93	8.49	8.19	8.04	8.62	8.71	8.32
Na ₂ O	3.12	2.91	2.90	2.81	3.18	2.82	2.65	2.41	2.91	2.57	3.30
K ₂ O	1.07	1.58	1.70	1.87	1.35	0.65	1.57	1.38	0.84	1.68	1.51
P ₂ O ₅	0.31	0.48	0.54	0.61	0.36	0.29	0.47	0.48	0.29	0.62	0.42
LOI	0.71	1.58	0.43	1.43	1.14	1.02	1.49	2.80	0.76	2.57	0.72
Total	99.99	99.64	99.65	99.52	99.32	99.66	99.69	99.67	100.04	99.53	99.70
Sc	20.8	20.5	20	20.5	20.5	22.3	20.7	21.2	21.7	19.9	21.2
V	174	189	202	215	178	183	204	209	179	216	192
Cr	223	231	236	259	216	227	236	238	216	275	304
Co	53.7	53.3	57.3	57.9	47.4	50.8	56.4	52.4	48.8	56.7	42.9
Ni	220	228	232	250	188	181	236	195	164	252	162
Cu	61.8	60.8	54.1	64.8	63.2	63.2	59.7	57.8	61.1	57.7	46.7
Zn	113	120	117	122	116	119	123	121	112	120	107
Ga	19.8	21	21.7	21.8	20.4	20.2	20.4	20.5	20.1	20.7	20.9
Rb	15.1	23.3	23.1	31	18.1	9.58	23.3	24	13.3	31.7	19.5
Sr	419	513	696	719	464	388	717	493	404	707	538

Y	20.6	24.7	22.6	24.3	23.9	23.1	24.7	24.9	22.1	23.2	21.1
Zr	136	222	203	249	168	135	194	196	136	237	165
Nb	17.8	35.3	42.9	47.6	23.3	16	34.8	35.6	16.3	46.2	26.5
Mo	1.41	1.13	2.37	3.09	1.49	1.11	1.31	1.75	1.19	2.16	1.58
Cs	0.0983	0.567	0.339	0.398	0.108	0.162	0.238	0.523	0.176	0.359	0.0693
Ba	235	359	515	503	314	195	414	408	207	559	366
La	15.4	28.3	31.1	36.3	21	13.7	27	27.6	14.1	35.9	21.1
Ce	32.8	58.8	62.2	73.9	44.4	30	55.9	56.9	30.5	73.4	42.7
Pr	4.2	7.36	7.55	8.85	5.56	3.98	6.87	6.98	4.01	8.86	5.4
Nd	18.5	30.9	31.2	36.2	23.4	18.2	29.1	29.5	18.1	36.6	23.2
Sm	4.49	6.66	6.73	7.45	5.52	4.84	6.48	6.64	4.7	7.61	5.44
Eu	1.56	2.13	2.18	2.36	1.78	1.69	2.08	2.14	1.64	2.37	1.83
Gd	4.71	6.38	6.2	6.82	5.55	5.25	6.3	6.38	5.09	6.75	5.39
Tb	0.732	0.932	0.898	0.968	0.842	0.817	0.942	0.942	0.785	0.961	0.813
Dy	4.03	4.93	4.67	5.07	4.62	4.53	5.01	5.02	4.33	4.93	4.32
Ho	0.746	0.892	0.831	0.891	0.853	0.846	0.904	0.908	0.809	0.854	0.778
Er	1.9	2.21	2	2.17	2.19	2.14	2.25	2.26	2.05	2.04	1.92
Tm	0.263	0.3	0.266	0.287	0.3	0.296	0.301	0.299	0.28	0.266	0.257
Yb	1.54	1.72	1.5	1.62	1.77	1.72	1.73	1.73	1.61	1.52	1.47
Lu	0.218	0.245	0.209	0.227	0.251	0.242	0.242	0.241	0.231	0.209	0.203
Hf	3.23	4.88	4.52	5.41	3.98	3.37	4.5	4.52	3.32	5.14	3.81
Ta	1.06	2.03	2.58	2.77	1.4	0.97	2.09	2.12	1.01	2.81	1.54
Pb	2.61	3.96	3.62	3.9	3.96	2.21	3.39	3.34	2.22	3.74	2.84
Th	2	3.49	3.79	4.2	2.57	1.54	3.28	3.33	1.61	4.06	2.52
U	0.543	0.51	0.839	1.12	0.61	0.406	0.904	0.9	0.414	1.08	0.615

$^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$	0.704290	0.704244	0.704005	0.704197	0.704446	0.704162	0.704407	0.704359	0.704287	0.704445	0.704183
2σ	0.000010	0.000010	0.000009	0.000008	0.000006	0.000006	0.000006	0.000006	0.000008	0.000007	0.000008
$^{143}\text{Nd}/^{144}\text{Nd}$	0.512778	0.512821	0.512853	0.512811	0.512747	0.512827	0.512835	0.512840	0.512843	0.512814	0.512814
2σ	0.000004	0.000004	0.000003	0.000004	0.000003	0.000003	0.000003	0.000004	0.000003	0.000004	0.000003
$^{176}\text{Hf}/^{177}\text{Hf}$	0.282964	0.282963	0.282991	0.282961	0.282949	0.283013	0.282985	0.282991	0.283016	0.282951	0.282983
2σ	0.000003	0.000004	0.000004	0.000004	0.000003	0.000003	0.000004	0.000003	0.000004	0.000004	0.000004
$^{206}\text{Pb}/^{204}\text{Pb}$	17.9370	17.8335	18.0625	17.9774	17.6895	17.9310	17.8834	17.8925	17.9475	17.9545	17.7747
2σ	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005	0.0004	0.0004
$^{207}\text{Pb}/^{204}\text{Pb}$	15.4956	15.4683	15.5028	15.4899	15.4534	15.4866	15.4746	15.4779	15.4936	15.4988	15.4776
2σ	0.0006	0.0005	0.0005	0.0004	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005
$^{208}\text{Pb}/^{204}\text{Pb}$	38.0934	37.9887	38.1469	38.0744	37.8544	38.0736	37.9858	37.9976	38.0996	38.0863	38.0841
2σ	0.0017	0.0015	0.0014	0.0012	0.0015	0.0013	0.0015	0.0015	0.0014	0.0015	0.0015
ϵNd	2.7	3.6	4.2	3.4	2.1	3.7	3.8	3.9	4.0	3.4	3.4
ϵHf	6.8	6.7	7.8	6.7	6.3	8.5	7.5	7.8	8.6	6.3	7.4
$\Delta\epsilon\text{Hf}$	1.2	-0.2	-0.2	0.0	1.6	1.4	0.1	0.2	1.0	-0.4	0.7
$\delta^{98/95}\text{Mo}$	-0.23	-0.32	-0.18	-0.26	-0.27	-0.36	-0.71	-0.54	-0.36	-0.49	-0.32
$2s$	0.07	0.06	0.05	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.06
Mo^*	1.34	1.05	2.30	3.09	1.46	1.01	1.25	1.68	1.15	2.14	1.51

	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2031	2033	2042	2043A	2043B
SiO2	48.93	48.98	49.91	49.56	47.73	49.97	46.15	49.07	49.42	49.33
TiO2	2.02	2.09	2.14	2.15	1.98	2.04	2.57	2.36	2.26	2.22
Al2O3	13.99	13.49	13.76	13.70	13.59	14.10	13.24	13.72	13.84	13.73
Fe2O3T	12.13	11.85	11.73	11.95	11.90	12.33	12.67	12.35	12.00	12.43
MnO	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.14	0.15	0.17	0.15	0.15
MgO	9.05	9.52	8.65	8.54	9.26	7.41	9.02	8.85	8.53	8.96
CaO	8.32	8.13	7.82	7.57	8.34	8.40	8.81	8.24	7.83	7.95
Na2O	3.06	3.05	3.23	3.14	2.89	3.07	2.44	3.15	3.22	3.11
K2O	1.48	1.69	1.75	1.71	1.52	0.99	1.54	1.61	1.66	1.54
P2O5	0.42	0.45	0.46	0.46	0.51	0.29	0.59	0.52	0.47	0.46
LOI	0.01	0.07	0.18	0.96	1.51	1.05	2.33	-0.13	0.30	-0.23
Total	99.56	99.47	99.78	99.90	99.39	99.79	99.50	99.92	99.69	99.66
Sc	20.5	19.9	19.1	19.2	20.8	22.8	20.3	19	19.7	19.4
V	189	187	187	187	174	187	203	192	187	187
Cr	269	311	275	280	266	244	219	272	282	283
Co	52.7	53.9	52	52.4	52.5	50.8	53.6	53.6	53.5	53.4
Ni	224	270	251	260	221	193	204	245	246	249
Cu	49.7	53.7	41.9	38.1	58.2	50.3	55.7	54.6	50.1	47
Zn	114	112	112	114	111	116	118	121	121	120
Ga	20.6	20.4	20.4	20.7	21.5	20.4	22	21.7	21.7	21.3
Rb	20.3	24.4	27.1	27.4	19.2	16.5	24.7	24.4	24.8	23.9
Sr	533	535	525	522	597	370	858	625	560	560
Y	22.5	22.1	22.6	22.9	22.8	23.4	23.6	24.7	24.9	24.9

Zr	159	165	173	173	174	145	226	214	205	200
Nb	28.6	31.6	32	32.4	31.2	18.5	45.8	36.5	32.4	31
Mo	1.72	1.94	1.88	1.86	1.48	1.34	2.06	2.09	1.38	1.35
Cs	0.157	0.205	0.149	0.161	0.215	0.258	0.296	0.147	0.119	0.111
Ba	336	409	391	401	286	210	385	421	397	355
La	21.2	22.5	23.2	23.4	25.6	16.8	33.2	29.2	28.7	27.5
Ce	42.4	43.8	46.3	46.7	51.8	32.9	67.5	59.2	55.4	54.5
Pr	5.28	5.52	5.73	5.84	6.33	4.51	8.14	7.35	7.17	6.88
Nd	22.7	23.5	24.4	24.9	26.7	20.1	33.9	31	30.1	29.2
Sm	5.3	5.48	5.64	5.78	5.95	5	7.29	6.92	6.69	6.5
Eu	1.77	1.82	1.86	1.89	1.95	1.69	2.34	2.14	2.07	2.03
Gd	5.39	5.46	5.59	5.71	5.78	5.26	6.71	6.53	6.44	6.34
Tb	0.812	0.827	0.848	0.859	0.863	0.827	0.973	0.965	0.945	0.931
Dy	4.4	4.36	4.45	4.51	4.57	4.55	4.92	4.97	4.96	4.84
Ho	0.804	0.794	0.809	0.82	0.827	0.848	0.873	0.894	0.903	0.889
Er	2.03	1.96	2	2.02	2.06	2.18	2.1	2.2	2.25	2.25
Tm	0.275	0.261	0.267	0.275	0.277	0.3	0.275	0.295	0.303	0.305
Yb	1.6	1.51	1.53	1.57	1.62	1.79	1.55	1.7	1.76	1.76
Lu	0.225	0.213	0.216	0.221	0.227	0.254	0.213	0.238	0.246	0.249
Hf	3.66	3.74	3.99	3.99	3.93	3.5	5.06	4.83	4.71	4.62
Ta	1.69	1.91	1.86	1.87	1.84	1.13	2.71	2.21	1.98	1.99
Pb	2.98	3.37	3.84	3.85	3.09	2.67	3.62	4.08	4.05	4.08
Th	2.62	3.13	3.35	3.36	3.01	1.86	3.99	3.52	3.33	3.25
U	0.769	0.824	0.751	0.668	0.83	0.509	1.08	0.899	0.575	0.474
⁸⁷ Sr/ ⁸⁶ Sr	0.704180	0.704155	0.704237	0.704217	0.703941	0.704254	0.704860	0.704284	0.704390	0.704353

2σ	0.000007	0.000005	0.000006	0.000007	0.000007	0.000007	0.000006	0.000007	0.000007	0.000008
¹⁴³ Nd/ ¹⁴⁴ Nd	0.512798	0.512789	0.512769	0.512763	0.512835	0.512790	0.512830	0.512767	0.512729	0.512737
2σ	0.000004	0.000003	0.000003	0.000003	0.000004	0.000003	0.000003	0.000004	0.000003	0.000004
¹⁷⁶ Hf/ ¹⁷⁷ Hf	0.282966	0.282958	0.282944	0.282944	0.282975	0.282987	0.282973	0.282937	0.282925	0.282920
2σ	0.000004	0.000003	0.000004	0.000004	0.000004	0.000004	0.000003	0.000003	0.000003	0.000004
²⁰⁶ Pb/ ²⁰⁴ Pb	17.5946	17.5026	17.4660	17.4710	17.7272		17.8131	17.5193		
2σ	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005		0.0005	0.0005		
²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²⁰⁴ Pb	15.4429	15.4337	15.4317	15.4332	15.4568		15.4851	15.4415		
2σ	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005		0.0005	0.0005		
²⁰⁸ Pb/ ²⁰⁴ Pb	37.8284	37.7152	37.7020	37.7046	37.9166		38.0132	37.7902		
2σ	0.0015	0.0014	0.0016	0.0016	0.0013		0.0015	0.0015		
εNd	3.1	2.9	2.6	2.4	3.8	3.0	3.8	2.5	1.8	1.9
εHf	6.9	6.6	6.1	6.1	7.2	7.6	7.1	5.9	5.4	5.2
ΔεHf	0.6	0.6	0.7	0.9	-0.2	1.6	-0.1	0.6	1.3	0.9
δ98/95Mo	-0.29	-0.37	-0.25	-0.46	-0.51	-0.22	-0.40	-0.51	-0.52	-0.69
2s	0.05	0.07	0.09	0.06	0.06	0.05	0.08	0.07	0.04	0.05
Mo*	1.71	1.94	1.86	1.86	1.43	1.30	2.04	2.08	1.37	1.25

Note: Mo* was measured by isotope dilution method. $Mg\# = Mg^{2+} / (Mg^{2+} + Fe^{2+}) \times 100$; $\delta Eu = Eu_N / (Sm_N \times Gd_N)^{1/2}$. Due to the short radiogenic time (2.8-9.7Ma) and thereby negligibly small radiogenic ingrowth, the initial Sr-Nd-Hf-Pb isotopic values of studied rocks were not calculated. $\epsilon Nd = [(^{143}Nd/^{144}Nd)_s / (^{143}Nd/^{144}Nd)_{CHUR} - 1] \times 10,000$. $\epsilon Hf = [(^{176}Hf/^{177}Hf)_s / (^{176}Hf/^{177}Hf)_{CHUR} - 1] \times 10,000$. $\Delta \epsilon Hf = \epsilon Hf - 1.59\epsilon Nd - 1.28$ (Chauvel et al., 2008).

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